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INTEGRATION OF ROMA: HISTORICAL, SOCIAL AND CULTURAL
DIMENSIONS

Compiled and edited by Ilona Tomova
and Lubomir Stoytchev

CONTENTS

<i>FOREWARD</i>	5
<i>ROMA DURING THE POST-COMMUNIST PERIOD</i>	
Ilona Tomova – Social Exclusion of Roma during the Post-Communist Period.....	7
Andrey Ivanov – Roma Poverty in Bulgaria: How to Understand It and What to Do about It?	31
Monica Rossi – In Transition: the Roma within the Bulgarian Educational System. Actions, Trials and Perspectives	64
Marko Hajdinjak, Maya Kosseva – Innovative Practices for Overcoming Social Inequalities: Analysis of the Situation in „Fakulteta“ and „Hristo Botev“ Neighbourhoods... ..	88
Boy an Zahariev – Egoism and Solidarity in a Shrinking Society.....	105
Stoyanka Cherkezova – Bulgaria’s Roma External Migration: Myths and Realities.....	122
Ilona Tomova – What if This Belgium Were in Bulgaria?! Migration of the Roma from Bulgaria to Belgium	145
<i>SOCIAL CONTEXT AND ROMA CULTURE</i>	
Ilona Tomova, Lubomir Stoytchev – Roma Representations in the District of Razgrad.....	175
Alexey Pamporov – The “Invisible” Islam (Syncretic Religious Beliefs and Practices among Bulgaria’s Roma).....	187
<i>HISTORY ANALYSES</i>	
Plamena Stoyanova – Social and Economic Changes in the Lives of Bulgarian Gypsy Population (1945 – 1989)	207
Maya Grekova – Gypsies as an Object of Assimilation Policy (from the end of 1950s until 1980s)	228
Velcho Krastev, Evgenia Ivanova – Participation of the Gypsies (Roma) in the Balkan War 1912-1913	247

**ROMA REPRESENTATIONS
IN THE DISTRICT OF RAZGRAD**

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***Abstract.** Pilot survey results concerning the Roma representations in the district of Razgrad are presented and discussed in the paper. The survey was conducted in late 2012 and the results show that for the last few years ethnic relations in the district of Razgrad have normalised and eased. The proportion of those who perceive as a problem the percentage of the minorities in Bulgaria has decreased since the early 1990s. First signs of a transition from traditional to modern forms of racisms (e.g. the latent racism) were detected in the study.*

Key words: Roma representations, social distances, stereotypes, prejudices

In 2012, a team of researchers from the Institute for Population and Human Studies at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences conducted a survey on the representations towards the Roma (i.e. descriptions, attributions, stereotypes, prejudices and social distances) in the district of Razgrad, north-eastern Bulgaria. Not only tens of questions concerning ethnic prejudices, social distances, etc. were explored but also the survey was aimed at detecting changes in the interethnic relations in the district for the first time after the Republic of Bulgaria joined the European Union in 2007. In this train of thought, we consider very productive for both laymen and professionals who would like to get as much as possible from our paper to rationalise the presented below results as a consequence of the complex interaction of values of a number of generations, each of which has accumulated its own historical experience, cultural specifics and more or less a unique perspective.

METHODOLOGICAL NOTES

In November 2012, a quantitative survey on representations towards the Roma was conducted in the district of Razgrad. Within a week, using a preliminary structured sample, based on social-demographic data for the district of Razgrad from the 2011 Census, the IPHS project team selected and interviewed respondents who represented different social and ethnic groups in the district of Razgrad.

A research team from the Department of Demography at the Institute for Population and Human Studies carried out the survey thanks to the logistic support of Integro Association. A detailed questionnaire containing predominantly five-level rating scales was designed; the major purpose of the questionnaire was to measure various aspects concerning the representations towards the Roma. Ten out of the seventy conducted interviews were pilot. All interviews were included in the statistical description and analysis as after the pilot results analysis was completed no significant modification were made in the questionnaire.

The good knowledge¹ about the structure of the population aged 18 and over (a dynamic population of approximately 100 thousand people) made it possible to reduce the sampling error to 7% in spite of the limited number respondents (for some items in the questionnaire the sampling error varies up to 11.7%).

Given the above, the presented survey results below should be referred to as comparatively conditional and they, respectively, suggest a number of reservations when it comes to interpretation. It is not by accident that we do not focus on particular numbers; the representativeness of the calculated numbers does not correspond to the highest research standards. The descriptions at hand should sound more like well-grounded hypotheses. Data were processed and analysed using the application package STATA, version 9.2. In addition to the one, two and multidimensional distributions, we have also employed an analytical method to calculate tetrachoric correlation coefficient for binary variables (Edwards and Edwards 1984).

ARE ETHNIC RELATIONS IN THE DISTRICT OF RAZGRAD BEING PROBLEMATISED?

The district of Razgrad can be described as a territory of rich ethnic diversity. It is one of the few Bulgarian districts in which ethnic Bulgarians are a minority. The largest ethnic group in the area are the Bulgarian Turks. Roma people are the third largest ethnic community (after the Turks and the Bulgarians). According to experts' estimates, more than three fourths of the Roma are more likely to identify themselves as Turks or Millet, Bulgarians or Wallachians than as Roma or Gypsies.

In the early 1990s, after the fall of Todor Zhivkov's regime, attempts for restoration of the abused rights of Bulgarian Turks were used for political mobilisation of people by the Bulgarian Socialist Party (BSP) and few newly-formed nationalistic organisations; as a result the so called "*Republic of Razgrad*" was founded. The local political elite, supported by a majority of ethnic Bulgarians, declared that they did not accept the changes which were being imposed: Muslims' right to restore their Muslim names, Muslims' right to speak their mother tongue outside their homes, their religious rights, the right to learn their mother tongue in public schools, the restoration of work rights to all released from work Bulgarian Turks who had filed requests

¹ The IPHS-BAS research team has conducted a number of fieldwork studies on the territory of the district of Razgrad.

to leave for Turkey and subsequently returned, the right of minorities to found their own civil and political organisations and restitution of residential property to the people who had been forced to sell their property in order to receive permission to leave for Turkey, etc. It was perceived as exceptionally painful when Bulgarian Turks took key political positions in the district: elected members of municipality councils, mayors and deputy mayors of municipalities, small towns and villages, administrative positions in local government, etc. For years, the ethnic tensions in the district of Razgrad were quite strong but mostly ethnic Bulgarians and Turks were concerned. The relations with the Roma were left behind and problematised by particular politicians predominantly in the discourse of “a threat to national interests concerning the *turkisation* of the Roma/Gypsies” or “unbearable social burden”.

According to experts, more than two-thirds of the Roma households in the district have at least one person aged 18 or over who lives or works abroad. As a rule, they financially support their close relatives who live in Bulgaria. In about half of the Roma households, one of the women is involved in the so called telephone marital fraud schemes, part of which provides comparatively high income. Given that, although official data show high unemployment among Roma², their financial situation is not much different from that of the rest of the population in the district; moreover, a substantial part of the Roma are significantly wealthier and have better living conditions compared to the other residents in the district.

According to experts, approximately 20% of the Roma in the district of Razgrad can be referred to as poor. These are predominantly people with low level of education and unskilled persons; families with a member who suffers serious illness or is addicted to alcohol; the residents of segregated neighbourhoods with difficult problems in terms of housing, education, socialisation and so forth; for example, such a neighbourhood is quarter “*Zapad*” (meaning West) in the town of Isparih. In addition, social workers and local administration officers emphasise that there are other vulnerable groups which face harder situation and, at the same time, have much more limited access to specialised social services: disabled people and those who suffer from serious chronic illnesses, a large part of the pensioners and a significant proportion of the unemployed rural population.

Survey results show that ethnic relations have been brought to normal and eased. Comparing the situation in the early 1990s, we observe that the percentage of those who dramatise “the large proportion of the minorities in Bulgaria” has plummeted. From statistical point of view, there are grounds to hypothesise that there is a new meaning to differences: in the early 1990s, the vast majority of ethnic Bulgarians in the district of Razgrad perceived differences only in the context of “a threat for the national interests” while, today, more than a half of the respondents declared that “heterogeneity is something good because it leads to cultural richness”.

Ethnic relations have been losing acuteness and are now sidestepped by other issues: high unemployment and impoverishment of many households, deteriorated quality of services, corruption, the poor quality of political elite and the great social

² According to NSI 2011 Census data, employment among those who identified themselves as Roma was only just 20.1% on national level and even lower: 18.2%, in the district of Razgrad.

inequalities. For instance, about four-fifths of the respondents identified mass unemployment and impoverishment in the district of Razgrad as a leading major issue and one of the most serious problems. This is easy to explain: as a consequence of deindustrialisation in the country and, particularly, in Razgrad district a large proportion of Razgrad residents have been in a situation of no permanent job for more than two decades. From demographic perspective, consequences are quite serious: for the period from 1988 to 2011, the population in the district has shrunk by 36.7%. Despite mass emigration, according to the 2011 Census data, employment rates in the district are extremely low – 49.1%, e.g. less than half of the economically active population are employed. The proportion of working poor is very high. A considerably large proportion of people (predominantly among the Roma and rural population) have no valid medical insurance which hinders their access to health care services. Since the number of children in rural schools has decreased a new organisation of educational process is introduced, which further deteriorates the quality of education. This very process is additionally being complicated by problems concerning the inclusion of children in pre-school education. A large proportion of Roma and Turkish children, especially in small towns and villages, can not speak Bulgarian when they start school.

The people of Razgrad district painfully make it through the “reform that never happened” in the country. About four-fifths of the respondents consider that social justice in Bulgaria has not been established: “laws are different for the rich and the poor”; government does not act in favour of the majority but on behalf of the affluent and those in power; bribes, corruption and nepotism are widespread and strongly affect social life; social rights of citizens are substantially restricted and not protected by the state. All these explain why none of the respondents asked to pinpoint three out of twelve most serious issues had identified the ethnic relations as a leading problem. About one-tenth of the interviewees responded that ethnic inequalities and potential conflicts were an important issue.

ROMA REPRESENTATIONS IN THE DISTRICT OF RAZGRAD

SOCIAL IMAGE OF THE ROMA

According to experts interviewed in 2012, the ethnic relations in the district of Razgrad can be referred to as quite good; social disparities among the large ethnic groups are small, there is no major social-economic inequality in terms of ethnicity. All residents in the district regardless of their ethnic origin have equal access to social services and discrimination cases generated by ethnicity are limited in number. Those working for the local administration and the interviewed police officers explained the situation of better ethnic relations in the district of Razgrad in comparison with the typical for the country mostly via the traits of the Roma groups in their district: “their Roma” are diligent, responsible and clean and only a very small proportion of them deal with thefts and frauds. Despite that, the interviewed NGO activists and the Roma categorically argued that social statuses of the ethnic

groups in Razgrad district are different. Furthermore, the survey results demonstrated that traditional stereotypes and prejudices towards the Roma, in addition to the disseminated by media and politicians negative representations about them, continue to strongly affect the way members of this group are perceived.

A number of items in the questionnaire were meant to construct the generalised social image of Roma. Positive answers to five statements provided for a positive social image. These were: „Roma people contribute to the cultural diversity and richness in our country“; „they give us a good example when it comes to taking care of elderly parents“; „they provide us the opportunity to prove that we are a tolerant society“; „they teach us how to value not only the economic aspects of life but also the social ones“ and „we can be proud that the Roma people prefer to live in our country“. Between a half (the first of the listed above items) and one-sixth (the last of the listed above items) were the proportions of respondents who supported these statements. On average, those who attributed positive social image to Roma are approximately 36.3% of all respondents. The proportion of those who waver appears to be rather high: between one-fourth and one-fifth.

Positive answers to five other statements were meant to describe the negative social image of the group. There were: „Roma people create a negative image about our country“; „they are not attached to our national identity“; „they are a personification of the lack of development (counter-development) in our country“; „if there were no Roma people in the country, racism would not have been a problem“ and „I feel ashamed because there are Roma people in our country“. More than 50% of the respondents replied positively to the first two of the above listed items while the last two items were positively supported by one-fifth and one-fourth of the respondents respectively. On average, the proportion of those who attributed negative social image to the Roma is larger: 42.3% of the respondents. The proportion of those who waver is smaller and varies between one-tenth and one-fourth.

NATURAL CREATURES OR A GROUP WITH SPECIFIC CULTURE?

All studies dedicated to representations of Roma in Bulgaria so far (since 1991) have disclosed that Bulgarians often ascribe many more and highly varied traits to themselves and to the Roma than they do to other traditional ethnic groups in the country such as Armenians, Wallachians, Jews, Gagauzians, Greeks, Karakachans, Tatars, Turks, etc. The survey in the district of Razgrad detected that respondents were still inclined to ascribe a great deal of attributions to Roma. It can be generalised that respondents' inclination to ascribe more negative than positive traits to the Roma community members leads to formation of negative or ambivalent attitudes towards them. At the same time, survey results provide us the grounds to hypothesise that the generalised image of Roma in the district of Razgrad can be referred to as more positive than their typical image on national level (which we have known for the last several years). This should be taken as an important inference which requires further research. It is also important and keep in mind that, as noted by social psychologists, modern racism is about reducing the frequency of ascription

of negative attributes to the stigmatised or discriminated group; but most importantly, the frequency of attribution of positive characteristics to the group is either decreased or very low (Austin and Worchel 1979; Diehl and Jonas, 1991; Forgas 1981; Nelson 2002; Tajfel 1982; Peabody 1985; Worchel and Rothgerber 1997 etc.).

Confirming previous studies, the project survey in the district of Razgrad clearly delineated a picture of respondents who are more likely to address Roma people using “natural” and “inherited” traits than “cultural” ones (Topalova 2002; Томова 2000). This very conclusion is valid for ascribing of both positive and negative attributions. The “naturally inherited” traits were ascribed more often than the “culturally acquired”. According to project survey data, four-fifths of the respondents ascribed “naturally positive” traits to Roma people such as musical, free-spirited, spontaneous, intuitive and handsome. The proportion of respondents who ascribed “negative” attributions to Roma people such as noisy, impulsive, instinctive, aggressive, wild and rude was virtually the same. The difference between the means of the naturally positive and the naturally negative attributions is approximately 2%. Three-fourths of the respondents described Roma people using culturally negative traits such as dishonest, revengeful, manipulative, malicious and shrewish/intractable. Three-fifths described them with culturally positive traits: communicative, preserving their self-identity, solidarity people, smart and creative; and the last two of the aforementioned attributions were chosen by less than 50% of the respondents.

Despite the limited number of respondents, we can clearly delineate groups whose representations about the Roma include all surveyed attributions distributed in one of the four types under discussion, e.g. “naturally positive”, “naturally negative”, “culturally positive” and “culturally negative” traits. Half of the respondents ascribed to Roma people all listed “naturally negative” traits, and between one-third and two-fifths ascribed all “naturally positive” traits. Between two-fifths and half of the respondents used all listed “culturally negative” traits to describe Roma people, and between one-fifth and one fourth ascribed all “culturally positive” attributions.

As expected, those who steadily ascribed positive traits to Roma were much more open to them. Only one-fifth of them hesitated to have or did not want Roma neighbours. On the other hand, those who steadily ascribed negative traits to members of the Roma community definitely rejected to have Roma neighbours twice as often.

Here comes the question about the causes which make Roma people unwanted neighbours for some of the residents (less than one-third) in the district of Razgrad. For now, it is hard to provide a satisfactory answer to the question at stake but the statistical correlation analysis we conducted showed that there existed a significant association between the unwillingness of respondents to have Roma neighbours and their reluctance to have people with large families as neighbours ($\rho=0.73$; $p<0.01$). In terms of neighbours, no other statistically significant associations were observed: the unwillingness of the residents in the district of Razgrad to have Roma neighbours has nothing or little to do with their unwillingness to have neighbours from other traditionally rejected groups for neighbours such as alcoholics, criminals and people inclined to conflicts. The most unwanted neighbours are the people inclined to conflicted, closely followed by the alcoholics.

Between two-fifths and half of those who steadily ascribe culturally positive traits to Roma people are likely to explain the lifestyle differences mostly via the discrimination against the Roma. Discrimination is the reason for lifestyle differences for almost one-fourth among those who steadily ascribe naturally negative and culturally negative traits to Roma people. The proportion of those who hesitate among them is also lower than among those who ascribe positive traits to Roma.

ROMA STEREOTYPES

The majority of respondents from the district of Razgrad share the widespread stereotypes and prejudices towards Roma people in the country. A great deal of them were formed or strengthened by prejudiced negatively stereotyped images about the Roma which are disseminated with impunity by media and politicians. These are stereotypes like: “the governmental officials do not observe their duties and let Roma people avoid responsibility for violations and breaches (unpaid utility bills, public transport free riding, acts of vandalism, etc.)”; “Roma are not law-abiding citizens and because of that they are dangerous for society”; “Bulgarians who live in villages are victims of thefts and violent offences committed by Roma”; “Roma embezzle social payments funds at the expense of the elderly, the disabled, the children and the single parent families”; “to a very high degree Roma people create insecurity in the public space through thefts, mendicancy, fraud and vandalism”; “a substantial proportion of Roma are careless parents”.

About two-thirds of the respondents expressed agreement with the above prejudices. At the same time, the interviewed experts argue that all these are not typical for Roma people in Razgrad district and very few members of the community commit crimes, violations of public order or abandon their children. Local residents formed many of these negative stereotypes during the years of transition as a result of a constant emphasis on the Roma ethnicity of a criminal perpetrator by media, policemen and politicians when somewhere around the country a delinquent act was committed. Instead of criticising legislative weaknesses or the lethargy and lack of qualification and coordination among institutions, media and politicians, government officers use Roma people as a scapegoat and further victimise them.

The heightened media attention to early marriages and childbirths, domestic violence and the cases when children were abandoned by the parents led to an increased stigmatisation of Roma. For years, media and politicians have been out of control in terms of hate-speech and even now this very type of control is rather weak and ineffective. This is how the ineffectiveness of institutions, the lack of professionalism among journalists and editors, the irresponsible conduct of politicians and the weakness of civil society contributed to preservation of the old and formation of new negative stereotypes and fears towards minorities and, particularly, towards the Roma in the country.

SOCIAL DISTANCES TOWARDS THE ROMA

Social distances disclose negativism towards a particular group as brightly as possible. Two groups of items were designed to measure negativism towards the Roma. Half of the items explored hypothetical symbolic rela-

tionships in which Roma people and respondents had equal social roles. Between one-fourth and one-third of the respondents declared their unwillingness to eat in a restaurant right next to Roma people, to become/stay friends with them, to sit right next to a person of Roma ancestry in public transport, to have Roma people living in their street, to be served by a Roma waiter/waitress in a restaurant and to share an office/work place with Roma people. The hypothetical situations which presumed very close relationships (e.g. to have a child of yours married to a Roma person and to have a roommate of Roma ancestry) were rejected by the majority of the respondents, de facto two-thirds of them. It is necessary to note that the social distances we measured seem shorter than the average for the country, measured in previous surveys. This makes it possible for us to hypothesise that Roma people in the district of Razgrad are better integrated than the average Roma person in the country.

The other group of items was designed to measure social distances towards the Roma when they were in hierarchical symbolic relationships with the respondents. We were mostly interested in what would be the proportion of those who rejected a Roma person to hold a superior position in relation to the interviewee in eight hypothetical social situations: the respondent to have a Roma music/dancing instructor, Roma officers in the army, a Roma person to teach the respondent's child at school, a neighbourhood police officer of Roma ancestry, a Roma person to become a judge, a minister of Roma ancestry in the government, respondent to report to a manager of Roma ancestry and a mayor of Roma ancestry. From one-fourth to two-fifths of the respondents rejected the first five of the listed hypothetical situations; the last three of the listed situations were rejected by a little over 50%. Despite the limited number of sampled respondents, there are statistical grounds to hypothesise that the social distances towards the Roma in the district of Razgrad when it comes to a hierarchical position are shorter than those in the country. For the purpose of a comparison, in 1998, when the above mentioned international comparative study supervised by Prof. Juan-Antonio Perez was conducted, three out of four Bulgarian respondents declared that they would not accept to report to a Roma manager, or to have for a governmental minister a person of Roma ancestry; and over two-thirds did not approve local police officers, military officers and their children's school teachers to be of Roma ancestry. This difference can be explained: in the district of Razgrad the social inequalities between Roma and non-Roma are not that large. Besides, it has been for decades since Roma policemen have been hired by the police and, according to their chiefs, they are among the top police officers in the district. The proportion of Roma who graduated from college/university has increased and these people now take superior positions in different sectors and industries in the town of Razgrad and other places: there are respected medical doctors and nurses in town, teachers, accountants, local administration officers, etc. of Roma ancestry. In other municipalities, Roma are elected municipal council members, mayors and deputy mayors of villages. They are deservedly respected and, usually, the majority of the residents of a village or a municipality voted for them. But yet, the positive image of Roma people and the good examples for experts and Roma governors have not been sufficiently disseminated both in the district and throughout the country as a whole. Even in the town of Razgrad, they are not visible enough in the public space: the majority prefers

to identify the Roma people who graduated from college/university and those who are highly qualified as Bulgarians and Turks, or at least not as “typical Roma”.

Another method of measurement of social distances was used: measurement of the level of identification or differentiation from the Roma. About half of the respondents replied positively to statements like “when I think about Roma people I feel them very different from me”; “Roma people cannot be trusted or relied on”; “Roma people’s fertility behaviour resembles that of rabbits”. Approximately half of them perceive the Roma as a threat to culture, social peace or the national security.

OPEN AND LATENT RACISM

We attempted to ascertain whether the negative attitude towards the Roma materialises via the traditional forms of open racism or has evolved to the modern manifestations which are typical of latent racism. In the late 1990s, the major difference between the Central and Eastern European countries and those in Western Europe could be summarised as follows: open racism manifestations towards Roma were characteristic of the CEE countries while forms of latent racism were typical of Western Europe (Perez 2000; Topalova 2002). Our survey data allow us to hypothesise that a transition towards the new forms of “modern racism” is undergoing in Bulgaria. Two-thirds of the respondents agreed with statements which disclosed latent racism towards the Roma people such as „Roma people do not care about the education of their children“, „they are less likely to pursue self-perfection than non-Roma people“, „Roma people are less interested in politics than the non-Roma“, „they care less about the welfare of our country than the other fellow-citizens“ and „they are less interested in environmental issues than the other fellow-citizens“. At the same time, only about one-third agreed to some extent with openly racist statements like „it is hard to imagine that I can have a Roma person as a close friend“, „Roma people are parasites“, „they should be made live like the rest of the people“ and „schools should have quota limiting the acceptance of more Roma children than it is admissible“.

The pilot survey provided an opportunity to examine whether people justify their racism speaking of it as something “natural”; moreover, who was to blame for the negative attitude and the discrimination against the Roma: the society or the victims themselves. In the district of Razgrad, about four-fifths of the respondents agreed with the statement that very few people really like the Roma. About two-thirds are likely to find the reason for that in the “deficits” of the Roma themselves: they do not care whether the rest of the people like them and this is why they do nothing in order to change themselves in the direction expected by the macro society; they like the way they live.

At the same time, the proportion of those who become aware that Roma people are badly treated, differently from the way others are treated, has surged up. Half of the respondents are likely to confess that negative stereotypes towards the Roma exist and traits which are intrinsic to a small part of the group are being unjustly ascribed to the whole community. This is how half of the respondents agree with statements like „only a small proportion of the Roma people beg or steal, the rest of them make

their living just like everyone else“ and „poor Roma are also disgusted by the dirt just like everyone else“. Two-thirds of the respondents agree with the statements that „non-Roma people cannot imagine how painful and humiliating is to be despised and rejected only because you are a Roma“ and „Bulgarians treat the Roma as second hand people“. It is clearly realised that Roma people are in a very difficult situation, especially when it comes to employment: four-fifths of the respondents reckon that „employers prefer to hire employees of different ancestry but no Roma“. Half of the interviewed reckon that „police officers are more likely to resort to violence towards a suspect of Roma ancestry than towards a suspect from the majority“ and that „media often use hate speech when it comes to Roma matters“. However, we are not in a position to argue that this humiliating and unequal treatment is realised and interpreted as discrimination; possibly, some of those who responded like this could be convinced that this is justified because of the actually existing deficits and shortcomings within the Roma community. We should not underestimate the fact that half of the respondents share the opinion imposed by media and particular politicians that „Roma people in this country are privileged“. We have grounds for our hesitation to define the recognition of unequal treatment towards the Roma only as realised discrimination: between a quarter and a half of the interviewed agreed that „Roma in Bulgaria are discriminated“ and that „the Roma live the way they live their lives because they are discriminated by the rest of the society“. Going beyond Bulgaria’s situation concerning the Roma issues, we asked the respondents for their opinion on the deportation of Bulgarian and Romanian Roma people from France and Italy in 2010: only a quarter of them defined the 2010 measures of the French and Italian governments as acts of discrimination. The rest of the interviewed were more likely to justify what was done as a measure taken according to the laws in the two West European countries.

ATTITUDE TOWARDS THE ROMA INTEGRATION POLICIES

Survey data provide grounds to hypothesise that the residents in the district of Razgrad better realise the necessity of a more resolute implementation of Roma integration policies than the average Bulgarian. Two-thirds of the respondents indirectly criticised the government and politicians when they agreed with the statement that “more political will and social actions are necessary in order to have the Roma people’s situation improved” and clearly indicated the nature of actions: “social programmes for employment should be expanded so they can reach all Roma”, “special educational programmes supporting the education of the Roma” and “Roma people should be encouraged to take more decision-making posts/positions”. It cannot go unnoticed that almost three-fourths of the respondents expressed an opinion that Roma people should have their own representatives in the National Assembly and in the local government bodies. They should also have rights to establish their own organisations and associations for preservation and development of culture. The majority of interviewees believe that Roma’s political representation should happen through the national political parties and they’d better not participate in political life via their own ethnic political party. However, the latter can be referred

to as conditional to a large extent because two-fifths of the respondents declared that Roma should have rights to establish their own political parties.

Two thirds argued that civil society should become active when it comes to support of the Roma: "we should express more solidarity when we see Roma people attempting to solve their own problems". Fifty percent agree with the statement that "we should value Roma culture and provide funding for its development" and those who hesitate how to respond to that question are approximately twenty percent. Policies that passively support the Roma via social payments or extended antidiscrimination legislation are not accepted: almost one-third of the respondents agreed with the statements that „government should provide more money for poverty reduction among the Roma people“ (understood as distribution of more social payments) and that „there should be more legislative acts against discrimination and they should be applied (for instance, people who rent flats should not be allowed to turn down Roma tenants who want to rent just because of their ethnicity)“.

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РЕПРЕЗЕНТАЦИИ ЗА РОМИТЕ В РАЗГРАДСКА ОБЛАСТ

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Резюме. Статията представя и коментира резултатите от извадково пилотно изследване на репрезентациите за ромите в Разградска област, реализирано в края на 2012 година. Резултатите показват, че през последните години етническите отношения в областта се нормализират и успокояват. Намалял делът на тези, които проблематизират относителния дял на малцинствата в България, сравнение с началото на 90-те години. Проведеното изследване отчита начални стъпки на преход от традиционни към модерни форми на расизъм.

Ключови думи: репрезентации за ромите, социални дистанции, стереотипи, предразсъдъци